

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSOCIATION OF STUDY YEAR WITH TYPE-A & TYPE-B
PERSONALITY IN THE MEDICAL STUDENTS AT MAYO
HOSPITAL, LAHORE: A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH**¹Dr Salman Falak, ²Dr Mohammad Qais, ³Dr Muhammad Masoom¹Medical Officer BHU Ghanian Ghazi Safdarabad²Isra University Hospital Hyderabad³PIMS Hospital Islamabad**Abstract:**

Objectives: To explore the incidences of Type-A and B personalities among the medical scholars of an institution and to find out the relationship among the personalities and the undergraduate students of different batches.

Methods: The design of the study was cross sectional and it was carried out in Mayo Hospital, Lahore which lasted for six months (September 2016 to February 2017). Sample was taken on the basis of probability systematic sampling and comprised of 500 subjects from each MBBS year. All the participating members and the administration of the institution were briefed about the purpose of the study and their consent was acknowledged. BECK Anxiety Inventory (BAI) questionnaire was used for collection of data. The respondents were segregated according to the personality types. SPSS was utilized for data analysis. In order to evaluate the relationship between the study year and personality brand, Chi-square test was conducted with 95% confidence level.

Results: The MBBS students in each year had Type-A students - 1st year (5, 1%), 2nd year (6, 1.2%), 3rd year (11, 2.2%), 4th year (13, 2.6%) and 5th year (19, 3.8%) respectively. The sample consisted of 54 Type-A students (10.8%) and 446 Type-B students (89.2%). Equal number of male and females were recruited for this study (250). Most of the Type-A personalities were among female students (29, 11.6%) as compared to male students (25, 10%). A strong connection was seen between the study year and personality type $p=0.010$ at CL of 95%.

Conclusion: The prevalence of Type-A students was confirmed in each MBBS year at Mayo Hospital, Lahore and a rise in the number of Type-A students was observed as the student reached final year of the MBBS. A strong relationship was seen among the study year and the Type-A personalities.

Key Words: Sample, Cross-sectional, Personality, Probability.

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Please cite this article in press Salman Falak et al., Association Of Study Year With Type-A & Type-B Personality In The Medical Students At Mayo Hospital, Lahore: A Cross-Sectional Research, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(06).

INTRODUCTION:

In 1959, two cardiologists explained the Type-A personality for the first time. They stated that Type-A behavior is most likely in people who try to achieve a number of objectives simultaneously by putting in aggressive, endless and non-stop efforts [1].

It has been verified by multiple researches that emotional fluctuations and behavior attributes contribute much in prevalence of cardio vascular diseases. Also, stress is closely related with the Type-A behavior and coronary artery disease [2]. Moreover, Type-A behavior pattern described by adherence to time deadlines, intolerance and aggression is surely related to CHD since 1950s. A study reported 13% injuries owing to hostile behavior [3].

Type-A people are generally categorized on the basis of intolerance, hostile, pushy, status and brand conscious and goal-oriented characteristics. Type-A people tend to achieve multiple goals in the same time by utilizing their workaholic nature [4] and dislike interruptions and uncertainties [5]. Contrary to Type-A behavior pattern (TABP), Type-B people are relaxed, calmed and do not necessarily adhere to time deadlines. Type-B personalities feel great on their achievements but feel relax if they are not achieved. Type-B are sometimes referred to as right brained thinkers [6].

Different parameters were used by researchers to check the type of personality. Type-A personality parameters might include time lines, aggression, involvement, job satisfaction, intolerance and better grades [7]. A research from USA delivered the personality disorders as high as 13.4% [8].

PDs association with cardiac diseases, depression and hypertension is well known [9]. However, a few researches showed PDs association with morbid circumstances. By employing the suitable intervention techniques for treatment of Type-A behavior, risk factors for cardiac diseases can be considerably minimized [10].

As the undergraduates in our set up will become the doctors in near future and serve for the treatment of the community therefore it is vital for them to be mentally healthy. If they possess a Type-A behavior, they won't be able to deliver at their optimum level. Due to the current situation in our country and increasing competition among different colleges and candidates Type-A students are under severe stress. The research in hand is focused on evaluating the

undergraduate students for their mental health and proposing the counter measures for Type-A personalities.

METHODS:

The design of the study was cross sectional and it was carried out in Mayo Hospital, Lahore which lasted for six months (September 2016 to February 2017). A total of 500 students (250 each gender) were selected for the study. The permission was obtained from the Ethical Committee of the college and all the students participating in the study were briefed about the purpose of the study and their verbal consent was obtained. Equal numbers of students (males and females) from each MBBS study year were selected by probability sampling. The students from all the MBBS programs were analyzed and those who were suffering from any medical condition were rejected for the study. Each MBBS program had got 200 male and female students. Initial selection was random but subsequently every 2nd student was considered to obtain the required sample size. BAI questionnaire was used for collection of data [11]. Students were categorized according to the BECK scale [12] and the results are tabulated below: (Table – I).

Table - I: BECK Interpretation Scale

Range of Scores	Anxiety Level
0 to 7	Minimal Level of anxiety
8 to 15	Mild Anxiety
16 to 25	Moderate Anxiety
26 to 63	Severe anxiety

The personality types were assigned to the selected sample on the grounds of criteria defined by the operational classifications. The students who scored 25 or below were marked as Type-B personality and the students who scored 26 or more were referred to as Type-A. Final decision for personality of the students was made after analyzing the BAI questionnaire filled by each member of the sample.

SPSS was used for data analysis. With the help of Chi square test relationship between personality Type-And study year was obtained whereas other qualitative variables like gender, MBBS duration and students' ages were represented in form of percentages and frequencies.

RESULTS:

The 500 students sample was analyzed for personality types and it was observed that 10.8% (54 students) were Type-A personality and 89.2% (446 students) were Type-B personality. The results are furnished in Table-II. Each MBBS study program had different

numbers of students for both personality types. The study year is given in Table – II.
year-wise personality data and its relationship with

Table – II: Frequency of type A and B personality among medical students

Student's MBBS Year	Type - A		Type - B	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
First Year	5	1	95	19
Second Year	6	1.2	94	18.8
Third Year	11	2.2	89	17.8
Fourth year	13	2.6	87	17.4
Fifth Year	19	3.8	81	16.2
Total	54	10.8	446	89.2

The sample was composed of 250 subjects from each gender. The Type-A personality was more common in females (29, 11.6%) as compared to males (25, 10%). Type-B personalities for females and males were (221, 88.4%) and (225, 90%) respectively. The difference between Type-A for males and females was not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION:

In our set up, the number of Type-A undergraduate medical students was observed. The Type-A personality increases as the student approaches final years of the course. The prevalence was more in female students as compared to male students. Many researches had yielded that the Type-A personality is somehow related to the cardiac diseases and therefore the issue must be resolved to overcome the personality issues especially in the people who are going to treat the public in later years.

The medical students have to study a lot. They use to read extra books, listen lectures, case-based articles and organizing all to grab a true picture of the subject. The teachers also prefer to create competition among the students by using different types of techniques and teaching methodologies which require extensive involvement of the students and they have to organize and push themselves to a level where they can be better off than other class fellows [13].

Personality disorders (PDs) were reported mainly in people with low education and residing alone (without family or partner) in the cities [8]. Another study conducted on medical students for evaluation of Type-A personality behavior concluded that the females are more likely to develop Type-A behavior as compared to males. The results are supported by the findings of our study where 11.6% females were observed with Type-A personality as compared with males (10%). Also, the students who spent greater time (6-10 years) in completing their degree have shown higher Type-A behavior as compared to student with less study years. Similarly, older students had higher Type-A behavior as compared to younger undergraduates. The study proposed that such students should be warned and briefed about the impact of Type-A behavior pattern on their physical and mental health [1]. Another study had reported the association of Type-A behavior pattern with myocardial infarction [2] but our study was limited to the personality types and its association with the study year (study duration).

A study proposed that the Type-A personalities should be briefed and awareness be disseminated to them regarding healthy living styles which help to reduce the Type-A scenario. Stress management should be employed to overcome the Type-A behavior. Regular exercise can reduce the stress level significantly [4]. Some studies delivered that the work environment is influenced by the Type-A behaviors. People working with such people hate their working style and often have strong disliking for Type-A personalities [3]. Our study did not encompass this aspect of work environment.

Another study has proved that the association of Type-A behaviors is strongly related to the CADs as compared to other personality types and a blockage of 75% in at least one artery was noticed in the subject study. Other variable factors can be included in a case control study to explore more relations to Type-A personalities.

The plus point of our study was the sample size and sample composition (each year medical students were included). Systematic sampling has minimized all the biases which might affect the results of the study. The study was conducted in a single medical institution therefore our study was limited. More concentrated results can be obtained by adding more variables and respondents from different medical institutions to ascertain a bigger picture to assess the relationship between personality types and study year. The data collected during the process of this work can be helpful in establishing a relationship between cardiac and other medical conditions and Type-A personality behavior patterns.

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence of Type-A students was confirmed in each MBBS year at Mayo Hospital, Lahore and a rise in the number of Type-A students was observed as the student reached final year of the MBBS. A strong relationship was seen among the study year and the Type-A personalities.

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